

THE CAVE OF SA OMU AND TZIU GIOVANNI MURGIA, FUNTANA ARRUBIA, NURALLAO (SOUTH-CENTRAL SARDINIA – ITALY): FIRST CONCLUSIONS

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Resumo: Os dados que aqui apresentamos são o resultado das primeiras intervenções no sítio Gruta Sa Omu and Tziu Giovanni Murgia, localizada em Funtana Arrubia, região de Nurallao (Sardenha). Estes trabalhos integram-se no projecto “Death materialization and life cycle (south-central Sardinia): Technologies and interdisciplinary studies in the detection and preservation of archaeological remains”, coordenado pelo Instituto Politécnico de Tomar. Este projecto interdisciplinar revelou-se necessário para a compreensão da ocupação humana no território de Nurallao, focando o período cronológico da pré-história ao período romano. Entre os diferentes objectivos, pretende-se compreender os cultos e rituais, as continuidades e descontinuidades, as relações entre os povos indígenas e os grupos ou civilizações que, a determinado momento, ocuparam estas regiões, bem como perceber as diferentes arquitecturas, ideologias e actos registados.

Abstract: With this paper we intend to present the first data of the archaeological works undertaken at the Cave Sa Omu and Tziu Giovanni Murgia, located in Funtana Arrubia area, Nurallao region (Sardinia). These works are integrated in the project “Death materialization and life cycle (south-central Sardinia): Technologies and interdisciplinary studies in the detection and preservation of archaeological remains”. This project stemmed from the need to investigate the human occupation of the Nurallao landscape, starting from prehistoric times until the Roman period. Some of our aims were to understand the rituals and cults, the changes and continuities, the relations between the indigenous and the cultures that, at certain time, start to occupy this regions, the architectures, ideologies and actions.

Key words: Bronze Age, cave, burials, trepanation, Sardinia region

INTRODUCTION

Sardinia as an island has elements that make easy to detect phenomena that differentiate themselves from other parts of Prehistoric Europe. However, it also reveals extraordinary situations that resemble the cultures and traditions of continental regions, due to the strengthening of contacts by sea routes that have occurred in the Mediterranean. But, at what level have they occurred? What is it that really characterizes the ancient’s prehistoric Sardinia groups? What is the relationship between them and the people who circulated at some point in the Mediterranean? We believe that to understand this issue we have to recognize and comprehend the perception of particular rituals,

especially those associated with death (these data are usually more resistant to), noting the influences, the differences and similarities observed in this type of deposition and their associated material culture.

Nurallao as a region is also presented as the perfect area for the study of this problem, since it is situated in the inner parts of the island (fig. 1), where traditional elements can easily survived and, in addition, large number of traces of this type are reported. In fact, throughout the Nurallao landscape several findings were recorded: several menhir statues, ten Nuraghi monuments (often in bad condition), the megalithic tomb of Aiodda, the sacred well of Nieddiu, two Giants tombs, three Roman graves and one from High Medieval age (fig. 2).

Figure 1 – Region of Nurallao and image of the Cava Sa Omu and Tziu Giovanni Murgia

Figure 2 – Archaeological remains in Nurallao region (Sardinia)

In addition to these monuments, some natural cavities with presence of archaeological remains, are present in

the countryside as well as is the case of the example we will now present.

The Cave of Sa Omu and Tziu Giovanni Murgia is a natural cavity where it was possible to detect a set of deposition and burial rituals associated with a material culture that we assign by comparison to the Bronze Age. The cave was first recognized as a potential archaeological site by Giusi Gradoli, in 2010. In October of that year, an intervention project was proposed under the direction of the archaeological works of the Polytechnic Institute of Tomar (Portugal) of which we will present now the first results.

GEOMORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOLOGY

The cave opens at the foot of a limestone formation, rich in organic remains, which is about 7.5 meters tall. At the top of the plateau a cascade leading to deposition of carbonate on the rituals depositions fell down. This natural waterfall lasted until 1968, were after the stream was deviated, leading to the extinction of the water fall. The blocks of rock on which the cascade fell, collapsed from the ceiling during the last decades, reducing the platform under which the initial ritual depositions were deposited. Thus, during pre-history, the cavity was different in shape, even if we do not know exactly how the access could look like, nor the proximity of the waterfall to the entrance of the cave.

From a morphological viewpoint, it is a 4 meters long and 2 meters width small cave, semi-oval in shape, oriented to the west, controlling visually an extensive landscaping (figs. 3 and 4). The deepest area of the cavity is slightly towards the area that gives access to about 50 cm and closes in a small room which gives access, laterally, to one very narrow gallery (fig. 5), which extends to the southeast. The same is true further west, in the area b). From what we could see, they do not seem linked. Its entrance opens onto a descending area that gives access to the nearby fields. Near the entrance it is possible to verify the presence of some large boulders coming from the fractured wall, already cited above, on which the cascade ran. They were in part recovered by the owner to build a drystone wall limiting the area of

the cave entrance, once used as shelter for grazing animals.

RITUALS DEPOSITIONS

With regard to the archaeological remains exhumed it was concluded that the cave was used primarily in the entrance area where the bodies were buried, while the gallery d) was specifically used for the deposition of the skulls. Here we collected three skulls, well preserved, one covered by carbonate re deposition, completed separated from their bodies, placed together near the south wall of the gallery. Separated from their bodies and skulls, three mandibles were found together in the input raster E2. However, during the anthropological analysis no exhumed skulls seems to belong to the gallery d). In addition to these three skulls other two were recovered, more damaged, during the first visit to the site, on the entrance of the cave, in the surface, and some fragments of skull and jaw, especially of children, retrieved from the heap of bones recorded in input. In the c) gallery we could see some animals bones on the surface, but they are intrusive. From what we could observe due to the narrowing of the opening, there are no human traces of anthropogenic deposition. The same happens in the cavity that gives us access to a) gallery, where only a small piece of prehistoric pottery was recorded. The b) area has some human bones and pottery fragments maybe resulting from the dispersal of the remains deposited near the cave entrance. In front of cave we found a pile of bones, disconnected, due to soil movement caused either by later occupations of the cave (including the present owner's one) either by roots of two holly trees that grew nearby there. However, it is evident the presence of some very small bones and some similar elements of the same body parts that allowed us to hypothesize a previous primary burials (fig. 6). The analysis of the skulls (fig. 7) and of some bones revealed that individuals of both sexes were buried there, with a minimal number of 7 adults and 2 children, one of which around 4 years old. In the adults bones, a great physical effort was revealed by some morphological

Figure 3 – Photo of the cave

Figure 4 – View from the cave to the landscape – direction W-SW

Figure 5 – Plant of the cave with representation of rock blocks and materials remains

Figure 6 – Plant of the cave with representation of material and osteological remains

Figure 7 – Image of the three skulls

characteristics of the humerus, ulna, phalanges or even of the insertion of the Achilles tendon (*enthesopathy*) (indicator of a major effort in walking, probably on rough terrain) and even in the head, justified by transportation of weights, as shown by arthritic changes on the occipital condyle. One of the skulls, an adult male, also have spicules on the front line of the frontal-temporal on both sides and another skull (adult male) showed two traumatic injuries during life. Another important point refers to a female skull (20 years old more or less) that revealed the presence of one single hole on the left supraorbital region. This is a trepanation, a practice that was relatively common in the populations of that time, in this region.

The study also revealed, from a humerus, that the male buried have a 1.65 m tall.

In association with the osteological depositions, animal bones depositions were recorded too showing us how, in the preliminary study, hunted animals (wild boar, rabbit) in association with domestic animals (sheep, goat) were deposited as well. Some bones of *prolagus sardus*, a sort of little rabbit, now extinct were also discovered.

As material culture recovered we can cite a large number of ring-shaped shell beads making some necklaces, a small set of various types of pendants, characteristic from Sardinia megalithic contexts, some ceramic fragments common to so-called Monte Claro culture (Lilliu, 1999), including fragments of three feet tripod vessels, as well as fragments of a decorated vase, with fishbone prints and three horizontal parallel lines along the edge, between each vertical segment registers a print dotted near of the last linear incision. This type of decoration is associated with the Final Bronze Age, like some few copies found at Castello-Lipari (Bernabo and Cavalier 1979; Cavalier e Depalmas 2008, pp. 294-298, Depalmas, 2009, pp. 146). There was also the presence of obsidian, including two blades and a flap element, and a blade flint too. In total there were 24 chips but mostly with no trace of use or retouch. From later period some pottery were found too, which could be assigned, for the type of ceramic, to classical times.

CONCLUSION

In the cave Sa Omu and Tziu Giovanni Murgia a set of artifacts, relatively low and simple, characteristic of the pre-funeral rituals recent prehistory, in the northern Sardinia were found. Fragments of pottery vessels were recovered point to an open, curved bodies with diameters of medium size, compact and homogeneous with folders, a minimum of seven units. The presence of ceramic decoration in fishbone, very similar to the type Cogotas Iberian element is an interesting development study. The same has been recognized elsewhere in Sardinia, mostly in residential sites, dating from the Late Bronze Age. Rituals similar to those seen here were recorded in other parts and are characteristic of the Bronze Age.

There are burials of at least two children and seven adults of both sexes, aged up to 35 years. Although the remains are raked enough, it seems it is some primary burials, by the presence of tiny bones and a connection of some anatomical parts of the body. A more careful analysis of the spatial position of osteological elements make us raise the hypothesis of deposition in the fetal position, facing north, lying on the left side. This type of position is very common in Monte Claro culture, especially in the southern parts of the island, having been noted, among other sites, in the hypogea and cysts at Sarroch and San Gemiliano – Sestu, as well as Corti-Becca Sanluri (Moravetti, 2009, pp. 101). The same is recorded in other parts of the island, as in La tomba I di Via Basilicata, Cagliari, (idem, 2009, pp. 103). Also the rituals of a trepanation of skulls recovered this (female, 20 years) are well documented during the Early Bronze Age, as is the case of Su Crucifissu Mannu and Sisa (Santoni, 2009, pp. 113).

With regard to the ritual separation of the skulls from their bodies and voluntary deposit elsewhere, the understanding is more complex. We know rituals of scarification involving symbolic acts and their deposition in ceramic containers, such as the example of Grotta Tanà di Carbonia (Lille 1988) and the Domus di Scab 'and Arriu-Siddi (Moravetti, 2009, pp. 101), and we have also a similar type of ritual of separation skulls from their bodies in the cave of Su Longu Fresu, in the mountain region of the Barbagia di Seulo (Central Sardinia), dated by AMS Radiocarbon of 4259-4042 cal BC (95.1% probability, OxA-X-2236-5315±36 BP), where there was found “at the far end of the cave, and facing the cave entrance, a heap of human skulls’ pieces with half a human skull at the base, now anchored in calcite flowstone” (Gradoli, 2011, 221), for this ritual deposition it was dug a pit and at its base in the floor where putted the human skulls. Also the authors found in association with the humans remains wild animals such deer, boar, mouflon and *Prologus Sardus* and domesticated sheep, goat and cattle. The material culture founded are characterized by tripod vessels like that ones that we found in cave Sa Omu and Tziu Giovanni Murgia. Although there are a few regional bibliographies were we could compare this remains and understand better this rituals actions, it is possible to understand how

complex is this social and ritual acts, only explained by sacred meanings and fait believes. To understand this acts we have also to understand the concept that are connected with the places where they are and the landscape that surround it. This restrict areas, connected with water (an important element for the life and probably because this a sacred element also important for the dead meaning rituals), hidden in the landscapes could represent the way or the form for materialize the message or the believes giving the sacredness needed and the required intent.

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